

APPLICATION OF HEALTH EDUCATION TO ANSWER SOCIAL INFORMATICS QUESTIONS TO CHANGE BEHAVIOUR IN THE ERA OF DIGITIZATION

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Abstract

The paper examines the application of health education to answer social informatics questions to change behaviour in the era of digitization, the aim of the paper is to enumerate the dilemmas of online and remote health education to change behaviour toward healthy practices and related literature were reviewed such as introduction, concept of health education, social informatics, principles of social informatics, behaviour change, behaviour change theories, stages and process of change, behaviour change in digital era, nexus between health education and social informatics, role of digitization in shaping health behaviour, application of health education in answering social informatics questions to change behaviour, policy and educational implication, of health informatics, conclusion and recommendation among which include: Health educators should adopt the use of smart phones, platforms and other related information and communication technology (ICT) tools in health advocacy for a better self and societal efficacy on health related behaviour change. Government, non-governmental organization and private individuals should provide information and communication technology (ICT) tools at a subsidized price for easy societal accessibility to health literacy such as smart phones, smart boards, city projectors and internet among others to change health behaviour.

Keywords: health education, social informatics, behaviour.

Introduction

Researchers in field of health education, computer science, information science, communications, sociology, anthropology, information systems, management science, education, and library science among others have been investigating the ways in which information and communication technology (ICT) and the people who design, manage and use them shape and influence each other in different social contexts. Approaching the problem from different theoretical and methodological perspectives, social informatics researchers attempt to understand the complex issues involved ICTs and their uses, challenge commonly held assumptions about information technologies and improve the lives of the people who work and play with ICTs. Social informatics

is further characterized by the problems being examined rather than by the theories or methods. Likewise, social informatics is similar to other fields that are defined by a problem area such as health education, human computer interaction, software engineering, urban studies and gerontology (the study of physical aspect of aging as well as mental, social, and societal implication of aging). Social informatics differs from fields such as operations research or linguistic analysis where methodologies define their focus and boundaries. Social informatics work is also empirically focused, that is to say social informatics research tries to make sense of annoyance to people when they work and live with systems in which advanced ICT are important and increasingly pervasive component (Steve & Howard 2000).

Research in social informatics can be categorized into three orientations that involve normative, analytical and critical orientations. The normative orientation refers to research that aims to recommend alternatives for professionals who design, implement, use or develop policy about ICTs and for health educators who uses this ICTs in health related information dissemination for different interactive sessions of health literacy and advocacy on diseases emergence, distribution and prevention in many societies regardless of the proximity despite the world become digitalised. This type of research also has an explicit goal of influencing practice by providing empirical evidence illustrating the varied outcomes that occur as people work with ICTs in a wide range of organizational and social contexts. Much of the work in participatory design focuses on identifying the variation in ways that users come to understand and adapt how they work through complex socio technical relationships. For example, unpredictable rapports usually exist between health education and society. While health education tailored it activities in addressing or mitigating societal issues of emergence, prevalence and prevention of diseases through social interactive information and communication technology (ICT) arena such as internet, google, satellite radio and television stations, social media like face book, whatapp, instagram, youtube, twitter to mention a few. The analytical orientation refers to studies that develop theories about ICTs in institutional and cultural contexts or to empirical studies that are organized to contribute to such theorizing. This type of research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how the evolution of ICT uses in a particular setting and how it can be generalized to ICTs of other settings. For instance in health education ICTs are usually adopted in advocacy and enlightenment on prevention of disease such as hepatitis, diabetes, tuberculosis, pneumonia indicating that, they are serious illnesses that hinder

wellbeing. The critical orientation also refers to examining ICTs from perspectives that do not automatically (uncritically) adopt the goals and beliefs of the groups that commission, design or implement specific ICTs. The critical orientation is possibly the most novel which encourages information professionals, health educators and researchers to examine ICTs from multiple perspectives and various people who use them in different contexts as well as people who design, implement or maintain them, to examine possible failure modes, service losses and idealized expectations of routine use(Sawyer & Jarrahi, 2014).

Concept of Health Education

According to Maria, et al (2019) health education is a continuous, dynamic, complex and planned teaching and learning process throughout the lifespan and in different settings that is implemented through an equitable and negotiated client and health professional (partnership) to facilitate and empower the person to promote/initiate lifestyle related behavioural changes that promote positive health status outcomes. Health education takes into account individuals/groups, internal and external factors that influence their health status through potentially improving their knowledge, skills, attitudes and beliefs in relation to their health related needs and behaviour within a positive health paradigm.

WHO, (2012), defined health education as consciously constructed opportunities for learning involving some form of communication designed to improve health literacy, including improving knowledge and developing life skills which are conducive to individual and community health.

Melissa & Artem, (2023), described health education as process of giving people the skills, tools and knowledge to live healthier. It has been proven to curtail early death, prevent diseases

and it is cheaper than treating the illnesses it prevents.

Concept of Social Informatics

Social informatics has been characterized by many names including the social analysis of computing, human centred computing, social studies of information technology and the sociology of computing. No matter the label, social informatics provides insights on computing that alternative approaches do not. For example, the rapid growth of social ware networking applications such as Friendster and LinkedIn cannot be understood solely as computational artefacts, mediated communication tools, useful and useable interfaces or as electronic exchange markets. Rather the variations in engaging and using these social ware networking applications to reflect a complex interaction of technological and social factors, including social communication norms, group communication expectations, perceived cost and value of communication and the presence or absence of other communication tools (Kling, 2007).

Sawyer & Jarrahi, (2014), described social informatics as the body of research and study that examines social aspects of computerization including the roles of information technology in social and organizational change and the uses of information technologies in social contexts as well as the ways that social organization of information technologies is influenced by social forces and social practices.

Kling, (2007), defined social informatics as the study of information and communication tools in cultural or institutional contexts. Another definition of Social informatics is the interdisciplinary study of the design, uses and consequences of information technologies that takes into account their interaction with institutional and cultural contexts.

Sawyer & Rosenbaum, (2000) described social informatics as a part of a larger body of socioeconomic research that examines the ways in which the technological artifact and human social context mutually constitute the information and communication technology ensemble.

Social informatics in the perspective of health education is described as a process that involve application of information and communication technology (ICT) in a social context to address health issues through the dilemmas of online or remote interaction for health literacy, advocacy, sensitization and interventional programs.

Principles of Social Informatics

Unpacking Google's plans to digitize research libraries a holding helps illustrate several principles that together define social informatics work. The various issues are raised to underscore that social informatics is problem oriented. This work is defined by its interest in particular issues and problems with computerization and not by its adherence to certain theories or particular methods (as operations research). The range of issues raised illustrates that social informaticians see computing as a web like arrangement of material artefacts such as computers and software, and the rules, norms and practices of people. These webs of computing are configurational in which their specific forms change over time and are intimately shaped by the social milieu in which they exist, webs of computing are however, path dependent in that previous actions and events guide, but do not predict the forms and shape of future actions and events. These characteristics are why social informaticians frame Google's digitization plan in terms of changing social norms, issues of copyright, access and fair use. Digitization is more than just a media decision but this perspective of Google's intentions raises

important and unresolved issues of use, access, design and policy in many diaspora particularly health education in detecting, predicting present and future happening about health and wellbeing in domains of epidemiological studies, health literacy, weather forecast, climate change, disease outbreak sensitization and control, pollution control, communicable and non-communicable disease surveillance and prevention. It is clear that, the technical act of digitization is possible (if laborious and based on many as yet unmade micro-design decisions). At the crux of Google's ambitious efforts however, are the tricky issues that deal with the social activities around these technical activities and ways in which what is social and what is technical interact. If Google's digitization project is seen primarily as a technical act, or if they mistake the deeply and broadly socio technical nature of this effort by seeing it as some sort of high quality interface design, they do little to increase the likelihood of the effort's long term success. Google is a smartly run organization so they are likely familiar with this insightful work (Steve, 2005).

Behaviour Change

Behavioural change can be a temporary or permanent effect that is considered a change in individual health related behaviour when composed to previous behaviour. It is sometimes considered a mental disorder, yet it is also a strategy used to improve such disorder. This change is generally characterised by change in thinking, interpretation, emotion or relationship toward healthy practices. These change can be either good or bad sometimes depending on which behaviour is been affected. It takes much more work to change behaviour for better than it does to experience a negative change. Medications can cause this change as a side effect while health literacy can cause this change to make healthier attitude and practice. The interaction between physiological processes and

their effects on individual's behaviour is the basis of psychophysiology (Bandura, 2007). Several theories exist as to why and how behavioural change can be affected and some of them were discussed below.

Behaviour Change Theories

According to Stephanie & Jeremy, (2019), Behaviour change theories aim to explain the mechanisms by which health behaviours change with a focus on harnessing those mechanisms to promote change. These theories trace their roots to early work in the field of psychology and B. F. Skinner's (BurrhusFrederic Skinner)work in operant conditioning, furthermore, Miller and Dollard's work on social learning and imitation which can be considered the first behaviour change theory asserting that people develop behavioural patterns through social interaction and reinforcement including observing the actions and consequences experienced by others. This work formed the basis of the modern social learning and social cognitive theories (Davis, et al. 2015).

Theory provides an organizing description of a system that accounts for what is known and explains, and predicts phenomena. For health behaviour change, theories provide a mechanism to encapsulate previous knowledge about how variations in causal factors (e.g., an intervention) produce a desired effect (e.g., behaviour change). Theory is useful because it provides explanations and predictions that support the generalization of findings from past work into future areas of inquiry and use (Eric, et al. 2019).

Social Learning and Social Cognitive Theory

Social learning theory sought to combine the behaviourist and cognitive theories of learning by positing that people learn through an interaction between cognitive factors, environmental influences and behaviour. Observational learning in this theory occurs with four processes: attention (observing the modelled behaviour e. g. hand washing in health

education), retention (remembering the modelled behaviour i.e performing regular hands washing to avoid becoming in contact with diseases), reproduction (attempting to imitate the behaviour i.e by practicing the act of regular hands washing) and motivation (anticipating the consequences of performing the behaviour including social consequences i.e to realize that if the hands are contaminated through social interaction can easily expose individual to many diseases such as cholera, diarrheal and hepatitis to mention a few). Reinforcement (external consequences) and self-control also play a role that is to there is need for precaution adherence. This theory was extended into social cognitive theory in 1986, an extensive theory of human motivation and action. In this theory, cognitive, environmental and behavioural determinants all interact and influence one another (Bandura, 2001).

People live and act within a social structure which is in turn influenced by its members. Human agency can be exercised by taking action, directing others or acting as part of a group. It encompasses intention and forethought, self-regulatory and self-reflective mechanisms. The latter includes the important psychological construct of self-efficacy where an individual's belief that, their actions can affect the desired change that can be capable of being effective in a particular task for example abstaining from unnecessary and unusual sexual intercourse interaction can prevent individual from HIV/AIDS exposure. The social cognitive theory is a general theory of behaviour not specific to health or behaviour change. Meanwhile, it is one of the most used theories in health behaviour change interventions including internet based health interventions. A shortcoming of the model is that, it ignores the role of emotions, neurology and physiology on behaviour. For example, behaviour often shifts as people age, without any

corresponding shift in social, cognitive, or environmental influences (Webb, et al, 2010).

Theory of Reasoned Action, Theory of Planned Behaviour and Reasoned Action Approach

Fishbein and Ajzen introduced the theory of reasoned action in 1967. The Theory of reasoned action arose from social psychology and theories of attitude particularly the theory of propositional control. It asserts that, behavioural intention (the intention to engage in behaviour) can be predicted by the person's attitude toward that behaviour and the subjective norm (perceived social pressure). Attitudes about performing an act are composed of beliefs about the consequences of the act, and the subjective evaluation of (or weight given to) these consequences. The model assumes perhaps unwisely that, behavioural intention is strongly correlated with actual behaviour e. g. most of the people involved in smoking cessation belief that is dangerous to life but due to the intention superseding they cannot abstain from that smoking (Sheeran & Webb, 2016).

The theory of reasoned action is probably best known in the field of health informatics for its influence on the development of the technology acceptance model (TAM) which asserts that, the behavioural intention of using a particular technology is predicted mainly by the user's attitude toward the technology (Reasoned Action Construct Attitude), which is in turn predicted by perceived usability and usefulness (Davis, 2009). The theory of reasoned action was succeeded in 1985 by the theory of planned behaviour, developed by Ajzen to improve the predictive accuracy of the model by adding perceived behavioural control (self-efficacy) and again drawn from social cognitive theory as a construct (Ajzen, 2010). The researchers' note that perceived behavioural control can influence all of the other factors in the model including

actually performing the behaviour (i.e. the individual may intend to perform the behaviour but ultimately does not do so because they feel they cannot.) The most recent version is the reasoned action approach which attempt to integrate the work of Fishbein, Ajzen, and several other models of behaviour change. It added beliefs about behaviour, norms and control as formative constructs and acknowledged the influence of external factors on shaping these beliefs. The reasoned action family of models are limited to reasoned action, implicitly a conscious process. It also posits that intention leads directly to action. This is often not the case because people sometimes engage in behaviours without conscious choice (e.g. habits) and frequently do not engage in behaviour despite good intentions (Prochaska & Diclemente, 2023).

Trans-theoretical model

According to Prochaska, et al. (2001), shortly before the publication of Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour in 1982 another highly influential model was introduced, this is Trans-theoretical or "stages of change" model. As the name implies, the model was developed through the integration of several behavioural and psychological models and proposed that behavioural change occurs in five stages. The stages are discussed below and final stage, termination was added later. The researchers also recognized many processes of change and noted that particular cognitive processes tend to be used at different stages of change. The verbal processes tend to play a large role in the early state of change. Self-revaluation and self-liberation tend to come into the action phase and counter conditioning and stimulus control bridge the action and maintenance phases. Social liberation plays a role in all phases of self-efficacy and temptation, (the strength of the desire to engage in the old behaviour) were added in later revisions of the model.

The trans-theoretical model has also been applied to and influenced research on organizational change and preparing individuals and organizations for changes in the workplace. "Resistance to change" is modelled as a mismatch between the readiness of the leadership for change and the stage of change of the health advocates. Studies across a range of behaviours show that before an action is taken, about 40% of health advocates are in the pre-contemplation stage, and thus will likely resist change if the organization leadership proposes it. This can be addressed by assessing the health advocates readiness to change and taking action (individualized or collectively) according to their stage of change, for example by activities which raise awareness of the need for change for health advocates in the pre-contemplation phase. The Trans-theoretical model portrays behaviour as mainly individual with social influences playing only a minor role. It also assumes that people plans changes before making them. And further suggested that five stages can be better modelled as only two: Motivational phase where a person prepares to change and volitional phase where a person executes the change (Armitage, 2009).

Stages of change

- a) Pre-contemplation: Not yet thinking about change or may not be aware that change is needed. For example an individual affected with hepatitis and not yet to think about the screening.
- b) Contemplation: Thinking about the change. Example, thinking about hepatitis screening.
- c) Preparation: Becoming determined to change. Example, ready to go for hepatitis screening.
- d) Action: Taking action to change. Example, to take all measures to cure hepatitis.
- e) Maintenance: Maintaining the new habit. Example, Constant adherence to the stated measures for hepatitis prevention.

- f) Termination: The new behaviour no longer requires active maintenance. Example, used to hepatitis preventive measures.

Processes of change

- a) Consciousness rising: Seeking information about the behaviour.
- b) Self -liberation: Belief in the ability to change.
- c) Social liberation: Seeking and recognizing social support for the new behaviour.
- d) Self-revaluation: Changing one’s self image in line with the new behaviour.
- e) Environmental revaluation: Seeking and recognizing the effect of the old and new behaviour on others.
- f) Counter-conditioning: Substituting new healthier behaviours for old habits.
- g) Stimulus control: Removing cues that trigger the old behaviour.
- h) Reinforcement management: Recognizing rewards from others and creating rewards for the new behaviour.
- i) Helping relationships: Seeking and recognizing support from others for the new behaviour.

Behavior Change in Digital Era

Digital behaviour change interventions (DBCIs) are interventions that employ digital technologies to encourage and support behaviour change that will promote and maintain health through primary or secondary prevention and management of health problems. Theories are keys to effectively personalizing DBCIs. DBCIs facilitate health promotion by providing support in the real world to change specific behaviours in specific contexts through the use of information and communication technology (ICTs) tools and are used by individuals. They increasingly use information about a person to adapt provision of support to the unique and often changing needs of the individual. One class of DBCIs is the just-in-time adaptive intervention (JITAI). A JITAI

provides support to individuals during just-in-time states when they have the opportunity to engage in a healthy behaviour (or vulnerability to a negative behaviour) and are receptive to support (Eric, et al. 2019).

Nexus between Health Education and Social Informatics

The connection between health education and social informatics is the application of information technology to improve health literacy, communication and patient outcomes within social and cultural contexts. Social informatics provides the framework to understand how technology is used in society, while health education uses this understanding to create more effective, accessible and context aware of health information and interventions. This intersection is crucial for developing technologies like health apps, patient portals and data analysis tools that are not only functional but also socially responsible and effective(Steve, 2005).

Role of Digitization in Shaping Health Behavior

The rapid advancement of digital technology has caused a revolution in healthcare as digital health platforms becoming key tools to improve health outcomes and shape behaviour, these platforms including mobile health apps, telemedicine and online health communities that enable users to access health information, personalized guidance and remote doctor consultations. In recent years, these platforms have gained momentum following the COVID-19 outbreak which prompted more people to adopt digital health solutions. New digital technology has brought about major shifts in healthcare. Tools like health apps, telemedicine wearable fitness devices, such as smart watches, smart phones, smart boards, city projectors, internet and online health communities have an impact on health outcomes and behaviour patterns. These innovations give users the ability

to access health data, receive tailored guidance, consult doctors and monitor their wellbeing. This development makes healthcare more accessible, efficient and patient centred. Digital health platforms are getting more popular for several reasons. More people are living with chronic conditions which result to a growing need for personalized healthcare and most folks now have easy access to smartphones and the internet (Tareq, 2025).

Application of Health Education in Answering Social Informatics Questions to Change Behaviour

Social informatics in health education explores how information and communication technology influence health behaviour change and also examines social, cultural and ethical implication of using information and communication technology in health. Below are some of social informatics questions.

1. How does health education address issue of unnecessary health related posting on social media?

Health education is a profession aimed at providing awareness to individuals in a community therefore, it is sacrosanct that whenever a health educator is across a posting on social media of health related pros or cons, he or she need to verify the information and immediately disseminate to the followers using evidence base strategies for them to realise that the information given to them is either true or false. For example individual may willingly decide to compose and post a statement on face book or other platform channels that “anti-snake flower is poisonous” and when eating by human can easy die, a statement like this is subject to verification in order to save many lives.

2. How can we ensure that digital health tools are design and implemented in a way

that is conducive and equitable for the community?

Health advocacy and policy enactment can be a panacea for ensuring digital health tools are design and implemented to improve and support stages of health care system in diagnosis, treatment and management of health condition such as smart phones and platforms, fitness trackers and smart watches, remote consultation through video calls, voice call and messaging, evidence based interventions delivered digitally to manage, treat and prevent medical condition are all used for health tracking, wellness management and communication about a particular disease like diabetes, hypertension, obesity, cholera outbreak, malaria, HIV/AIDS to mention a few.

3. How does social and economic factor influence access to and use of health information and communication technology, Example considering internet access, digital literacy, and affordability of devices?

The world has now become a global village where information about health related advantages and disadvantages can reach individuals in a short period of time regardless of individual economic status or proximity where one can have access to health information via internet through Google and explorer, digital literacy through radio and television stations, social media such as face book, whatapp, instagram, twitter, among others. Meanwhile, this communication channels are very affordable and accessible to even a common persons in the community.

4. How online health communities and social media influence health related behaviour and decision making?

Many online channels for dissemination of health related information now exist where conversation among interactive individual in the community become so easier regardless of the proximity, individuals are usually enlighten via

online dilemmas such as Google or zoom meeting, video and voice calls, tiktok, instagram, face books to mention a few which at the end may influence behaviour change and aid in sound decision making. For example during covid-19 pandemic the above mention dilemmas where used to effectively communicate to the members of the community in taking necessary precautions in order to prevent them self from becoming infected with virus while they are at home.

5. How can we use artificial intelligence to improve effectiveness and efficiency of health care delivery?

Artificial intelligence has become more integrated phenomena in the current situation where it can be used to solve diversity of problems particularly health issues, artificial intelligence is used in health care for information management, information dissemination, plastic surgeries such as appendectomy and others operations, disease determination, disease surveillance, disease diagnosis, virtual enlightenment and control of communicable and non-communicable disease among others.

6. What are the ethical implications of using technology in health care system and how can we ensure that it does not exacerbate existing health disparities?

Ethical implications of using technology concern about patient information privacy and security despite health informatics through information and communication technology deals with a large amount of data, it is also important to inform consent on emergence of new innovative technologies so that they will not feel bias and by establishing an understandable accountability to minimise errors and maintenance of human element in relationships with patients that is to say patients should be given autonomy for the right of self-determination including views and decision.

Policy and Educational Implication of Health Informatics

One of the reasons for slow progress in the development of healthcare information systems policy and the accompanying need to provide education and training must certainly be the magnitude of the problems of policy and educational implication. Barrier involves the confusion that continues to exist between the various terms used in the healthcare information business. Examples include the synonymous use of the terms medical informatics, healthcare information management, healthcare informatics and medical librarianship (Norris&Brittain,2000).

Conclusion

Social informatics have been investigating the ways in which information and communication technology (ICT) and the people who design, manage and use them shape and influence each other in different social contexts. Approaching the problem from different theoretical and methodological perspectives, computers and internet have become more integrated into our lives through attractive platforms for health behaviour change interventions, and many computer based interventions provide information with theory guiding what information is presented, to whom and in what ways to use. In the current era, the world become a global village where information and communication technology (ICT) tools where employed to ease social interaction among individuals using a dilemmas of either online or remote health literacy and advocacy which serve as a paramount key in health related behaviour change. It is belief that use of modern information technology tools will serve as panacea for solving health care problems such as smart phones, smart watches in diagnosis of diseases, monitoring body temperature,

measuring level of diabetes, hepatitis and online consultations.

Recommendations

The paper recommended the following suggestions;

1. Health educators should emphasise the use of internet often which many health programmes can be tailored to in the perspective of disease prevention, health literacy and health advocacy.
2. Health educators should adopt the use of smart phones, platforms and other related information and communication technology (ICT) tools in health advocacy for a better self and societal efficacy on health related behaviour change.
3. Government, non-governmental organization and private individuals should provide information and communication technology (ICT) tools at a subsidized price for easy societal accessibility to health literacy such as smart phones, smart boards, city projectors and internet among others to change health behaviour.
4. Policy makers should ensure proper education and training of health educators and by providing them with necessary ICTs tools for a better and disease free nation.

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